

Tools and resources for diachronic lexical semantic analyses: state of the art

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Introduction	1
1. Semantically annotated corpora	2
1.1 Corpora annotated with senses.....	2
1.1.1 Annotation using WordNet.....	2
1.1.2 Annotation using other lexical resources and ontologies.....	4
2. Lexica and databases	6
3. Digital editions linked to lexicographic resources	7
4. Tools for automatic semantic annotation	7
5. Tools for manual semantic annotation	8
6. Approaches to semantic change analysis	9
Acknowledgements	10
References	10

Introduction

In this document we intend to outline the state of the art on the existing tools and resources for research on lexical semantic change. This report was conceived in the framework of the project ‘A new CLARIN Resource Family for lexical semantic change research’ funded by CLARIN-ERIC, which spans from November 2022 to June 2023. The project is led by Barbara McGillivray (King’s College London) and Fahad Khan (ILC-CNR), with Paola Marongiu (University of Neuchâtel) as research assistant. One of the aims of the project is to provide documentation on the existing resources for diachronic lexical semantic analysis, in order to support the creation of a new CLARIN Resource Family for lexical semantic change research. Automatic semantic change detection has been extensively covered in recent works, for instance in Teodorescu et al. (2022), Tahmasebi et al. (2021), and the dedicated SemEval shared task (Schlechtweg et al. 2020) among others. In our research we want to focus on semantic change at the level of word senses and semantic classes (see e.g. Juvonen & Koptjevskaja-Tamm, 2016). This document presents a survey on existing resources for (diachronic) lexical semantic analyses: we will cover corpora annotated with word senses, lexica and databases and tools for automatic annotation of word senses. Although not strictly related with word senses, we also will briefly mention resources that present other types of semantic annotation e.g. semantic roles, information structure or named entity recognition.

The document is structured as follows.

The first section is dedicated to corpora semantically annotated. This includes corpora annotated with senses, with various lexical resources, and corpora annotated with other types of semantic information.

The second section is devoted to illustrate existing lexical resources such as dictionaries, lexica, wordlists.

The third section briefly illustrates another type of resource which can include semantic information, but which does not fall into the category of corpora, that is, digital editions.

The fourth and fifth sections are dedicated to tools for respectively automatic and manual sense annotation.

Finally, in the sixth section we offer an example of how lexical semantic change analysis can be performed with the tools illustrated throughout the survey.

1. Semantically annotated corpora

In this section we will describe existing semantically annotated corpora, expanding on the two valuable surveys by Petrolito and Bond (2014), and Pasini and Camacho-Collados (2020).

The first subsection will be devoted to the description of corpora annotated with word senses: in this type of resources, target lexical units (or all the lexical units in the texts) are annotated with the most appropriate sense in context.

The second subsection will describe other corpora in which other types of semantic features have been annotated e.g. semantic roles, information structure. In some cases, this type of annotation exceeds the limits of the lexical unit and is based on larger units of annotation e.g. in the case of corpora annotated with modality.

1.1 Corpora annotated with senses

The corpora described in this subsection are grouped based on the type of resource used for determining the senses that should be associated with each lexical unit. WordNet (Fellbaum 1998) is a lexical database of around 100,000 English lemmas in which senses are organised based on semantic relations of hyponymy, hyperonymy and synonymy. The English WordNet has been translated into several languages, such as Latin (Minozzi 2010; Biagetti et al. 2021).

1.1.1 Annotation using WordNet

Several sense-level annotated corpora were created by using the synsets extracted from the existing WordNet for the language of reference.

The Semcor corpus (Miller et al. 1993) was created at Princeton University by the same team that was working on the English WordNet (Landes et al. 1998). SemCor is a corpus manually annotated at the sense level by using the English WordNet. It consists of a subset of 374 texts from the Brown corpus (Francis and Kucera, 1979) and counts 664,038 words, 200,000 of which have been annotated with senses. SemCor is an all-word sense-annotated corpus and the annotation was created through sequential tagging. The English SemCor represents a milestone in this field because it is one of the first corpora annotated with senses at the word level, and the first one annotated by using WordNet. After SemCor, similar corpora have been created for different languages:

1. Arabic: the AQMAR Arabic Wikipedia Supersense Corpus (Schneider et al. 2012) consists of 28 Wikipedia articles in Arabic for a total of 65,000 tokens, of which 32,000 have been annotated manually with supersenses retrieved from the English WordNet. The supersense tags define 40 lexical semantic classes (25 for nouns and 15 for verbs) e.g. ANIMAL, PLANT, BODY, FOOD etc. The authors provide guidelines for manual annotation of supersenses that are intended to be language independent.
2. Bulgarian: BulSemCor (Koeva et al., 2010) was developed based on BulNet, the Bulgarian WordNet (Koeva et al. 2004). It is part of the Bulgarian Brown corpus (Stoyanova et al. 2006) and it consists of 95,119 words.
3. Basque: EuSemCor (Agirre et al. 2006) was created by manually annotating a corpus using the Basque WordNet (Agirre et al. 2002), and it consists of around 300,000 words. The sense inventory for each word is determined based on the lexicographic description in a dictionary of reference for Basque. The annotation was performed by two annotators, and a third one was in charge of reviewing the cases of disagreement and providing an unambiguous annotation.
4. Catalan and Spanish: AnCora-CAT and AnCora-ESP (Taulé et al., 2008) are two corpora of respectively Catalan and Spanish texts, which count 500 words each. The texts are annotated with lemma, PoS, morphology and syntax. Semantic annotation concerns the semantic class and argument structure of verbs, named entities and, only for nouns, word senses. The semantic annotation was performed manually, by using the Spanish and Catalan EuroWordNets for the sense inventory.
5. German: there are two corpora annotated with senses for German, TüBa-D/Z Treebank and WebCaGe. The TüBa-D/Z Treebank (Henrich and Hinrichs, 2014) is a manually annotated treebank with senses taken from GermaNet (Hamp, B. & H. Feldweg, 1997), the German WordNet. It counts 18,000 tokens and is based on a corpus of German newspapers. It currently represents the largest manually sense-annotated corpus for German. WebCaGe (Henrich et al. 2012) is short for *Web-Harvested Corpus Annotated with GermaNet Senses* and it is a corpus of 10,750 annotated words. The annotated corpus was created entirely automatically, mapping GermNet synsets with the sense definitions in Wiktionary¹, in order to have Wiktionary sense descriptions paired up with GermaNet senses. Since GermaNet is used as a sense inventory, and WebCaGe was conceived primarily for the word sense disambiguation task, the target words are all the words that are assigned at least two senses in GermaNet. The corpus counts 10,750 annotated tokens.
6. Hungarian: Hungarian WSD (Vincze et al. 2008) contains texts from the Hungarian National Corpus (Oravecz et al. 2014), manually annotated by word senses. The annotation was performed by two annotators on a selection of 39 target words. A third annotator was in charge of disambiguating cases of disagreement between the two annotators. The corpus contains 5,000 sense-annotated words. The source of the sense inventory was The Concise Dictionary of the Hungarian language. As the annotation progressed, the Hungarian WordNet (Hatvani et al. 2007) was enriched with new senses annotated in the corpus.
7. Italian: the ISST-Italian Semantic-Syntactic Treebank (Montemagni et al. 2003) is a treebank in which adjectives, nouns and verbs have been manually annotated with word senses (partially annotated with other resources), for a total of 81,236 sense-annotated

¹ Wiktionary is a web-based dictionary freely available online and updated collaboratively by volunteers. Wiktionary contains information about part-of-speech, inflection, translations and the meanings are described by providing sentences that illustrate the use of the sense in context.

- words. The source for the sense inventory is the ItalWordNet, the Italian section of the EuroWordNet (Roventini et al. 2000).
8. Polish: the KPWr–Polish Corpus of the Wrocław University of Technology (Broda et al. 2012, Marcińczuk et al. 2015) is a corpus of 1,127 Polish texts, for a total of 438,000 words, of which 9,000 have been sense-annotated by using the Polish WordNet PIWN (Maziarz et al. 2016) for the sense inventory. The annotation has been performed manually on a selection of 74 target words (45 nouns and 29 verbs).
 9. Slovenian: jos100k (Erjavec et al. 2010) is a corpus of texts in Slovenian, counting 100,000 words. The corpus is annotated at the word sense level. 5,000 words have been manually annotated by using the Slovenian WordNet (SloWN) for the word sense inventory.
 10. Spanish: SpSemCor (Castellón et al. 2012) is a Spanish corpus in which a selection of 3,693 nouns has been sense-annotated. The sense inventory is based on the Spanish WordNet (Atserias et al., 2004). SpSemCor is part of the larger corpus SenSem (Alonso et al. 2007), which is a resource in which the 250 most frequent Spanish verbs are tagged with verb sense, construction type, aspect, argument functions and semantic roles. The sentences containing the target verbs are mapped onto a verbal database. The aim of SpSemCor is to provide semantic annotation for the nominal heads of the verbal arguments of the SenSem corpus. The annotation of SpSemCor was performed manually and by presenting the annotator with all the occurrences of a target word in the corpus (targeted tagging).

Starting from the English SemCor, several multilingual corpora annotated by senses have been developed. En-Ro SemCor is a multilingual corpus of English and Romanian texts. The corpus contains 178,499 words for English and 175,603 words for Romanian (Lupu et al., 2005; Ion, 2007). The English SemCor texts were translated into Romanian and the senses were transferred from English to Romanian with WSDTool, an algorithm for word sense disambiguation (Ion 2007). Another example is MultiSemCor+ corpus (Bentivogli and Pianta, 2005), which collects texts in English and Italian, annotated at the sense level. The corpus was built by using the annotation transfer method: the annotation performed on the source text is projected onto the target text. In this case, the English SemCor was used as a starting point to project the annotation of word senses onto the Italian corpus. The same method was applied to the development of JSemCor (Bond et al. 2012), a corpus for Japanese. JSemCor counts around 58,000 words and it was created by projecting the annotation of the English SemCor onto the Japanese text. The annotation of JSemCor was also functional to the development and improvement of the Japanese WordNet (Bond et al. 2010).

1.1.2 Annotation using other lexical resources and ontologies

There are other sense-annotated corpora which are based on other lexical resources and ontologies.

One of them is the EuroSense (Delli Bovi et al., 2017) corpus, which was created by using BabelNet (Navigli & Ponzetto, 2012). BabelNet is a semantic network that was created by linking various encyclopedias and dictionaries e.g. Wikipedia and WordNet. Therefore it provides both lexical and encyclopedic knowledge, and as a multilingual resource it was used to annotate corpora in different languages. Among them, the EuroSense corpus is a corpus annotated with senses for 21 languages. The annotation of the corpus ACL-RelAcS (Gábor et al. 2016) also partially relied on BabelNet. ACL-RelAcS is a corpus of 4,200,000 words, which collects around 11,000 abstracts of the Association of Computational Linguistics. Concepts in this corpus were automatically annotated

with BabelNet. Other corpora annotated with BabelNet are SenseDefs (Camacho-Collados et al., 2019), Train-o-Matic (Pasini and Navigli, 2017) and OneSec (Scarlini et al., 2019).

Wikipedia was also used for sense annotation in the Semantically Enriched Wikipedia corpus (SEW, Raganato et al. 2016). Wikipedia represents a multilingual encyclopedic resource which covers a large number of concepts and entities. The SEW is a corpus annotated with word senses by using Wikipedia hyperlinks. It contains more than 160,000,000 sense annotations.

Besides BabelNet and Wikipedia, the annotation of other corpora has sometimes relied on language-specific resources. DutchSemCor (Vossen et al. 2011; Vossen et al. 2012) is a corpus of Dutch texts (one million tokens) annotated at the word sense level, by using the lexical database Cornetto (Vossen 2006). Cornetto is built by combining the Dutch WordNet (Vossen 1998) with the Referentie Bestand Nederlands (Maks et al. 1999), which includes information about semantic frames as in the English FrameNet (Fillmore et al. 2004). The annotation of part of the DutchSemCor was performed manually by two annotators. The annotators annotated 282,503 tokens for a total of 11,982 senses. They were instructed to annotate 25 examples for each sense. The examples were selected using a sense annotation tool (SAT) (Görög and Vossen 2010; Van Gompel 2010; Vossen et al. 2011). The inter-annotator agreement is 94%. The high score is given by the fact that the annotators were encouraged to discard all the ambiguous examples and to annotate contexts where the sense was clearly identifiable. The other part of the corpus was tagged by using tagging systems trained on manually annotated data and other data gathered with bootstrapping (Görög and Vossen 2010). The WSD system is the TIMBL WSD (see section 4).

In McGillivray et al. (2021), a subset of 40 words of the LatinISE corpus (McGillivray and Kilgariff 2013) was manually annotated with word senses. The words were selected based on the presence or absence of some type of semantic change. One of the selected words was *dux* 'leader' which changes its meaning to 'duke' (Clackson 2011; Clackson and Horrocks 2007). The sense inventory provided to the annotators for each word was built based on the Latin dictionaries Lewis & Short (1879), Lewis (1890) and Du Cange et al. (1883–1887 [1678]). Not all the occurrences of the target words were annotated: 60 passages were randomly extracted from LatinISE for each target word and given to the annotators. The passage included the right and left context for the target word and the inventory of senses. No indication was given concerning the date of the text, its author or title. The annotation followed the DuRel annotation framework (Schlechtweg et al. 2018), which proposes a graded annotation where annotators assign a value from 1 to 4 to each sense in the sense inventory for each passage. The grades indicate how closely the meaning of the target word in a specific passage expresses each sense provided in the inventory (1 corresponding to 'Unrelated' and 4 to 'Identical').

1.2 Corpora annotated with other types of semantic information (not word senses)

While our primary focus is on resources annotated at the word sense level, it is important to acknowledge the existence of other types of semantically annotated resources for various languages, which focus on semantic features other than lexical semantics. Therefore, we will provide a brief overview of such resources in this section.

Some work has been done on semantic annotation of corpora for historical languages, Latin and Ancient Greek in particular. The PROIEL (Haug & Jøhndal, 2018) treebank collects texts in Latin

(225,064 tokens) and Ancient Greek (250,455 tokens). The Latin portion of this treebank presents a semantically annotated layer that includes the features of animacy, information structure and anaphora. The annotation concerns nominal lemmata and the number of lexical items annotated was 1745 in 2019 (last update), mainly in Biblical language. The PROIEL treebank for Ancient Greek only contains annotations on the information structure. For both treebanks the semantic annotation has been performed manually and is available upon request.

The Index Thomisticus Treebank (IT-TB) (Passarotti, 2019) is a corpus collecting texts by Thomas Aquinas encompassing a total of 350,000 tokens. The corpus was originally annotated according to the Prague Dependency Treebank (PDT) style, and then converted into the Universal Dependencies annotation style (Cecchini et al., 2018). A portion of the IT-TB (28,000 tokens) was annotated to the tectogrammatical layer in the PDT style. This layer is built upon the morphological layer, containing information about lemmas and morphology, as well as the analytical layer, encoding syntactic information through dependency trees. The tectogrammatical layer presents additional semantic/pragmatic information. In this layer, the sentence's underlying structure is represented by tectogrammatical trees, where the nodes correspond to content words exclusively. Each node is assigned a semantic role label called 'functor,' which specifies the semantic role of a mandatory argument (e.g., 'Actor' or 'Patient') or the type of adverbial (e.g., 'Place' or 'Manner'). Other types of semantic information included in the tectogrammatical layer are: the illocutionary force of the sentence; ellipsis resolution, performed by adding new empty nodes; coreference analysis, with arrows connecting the nodes involved in coreference relations.

The AGLDT (Perseus Treebank, Bamman and Crane 2011) is a treebank of Latin and Ancient Greek, including 79,697 tokens for Latin and 557,922 tokens for Ancient Greek. A small portion of the Greek texts, namely Aesop's Fables and Diodorus Siculus *Bibliotheca Historica*, present an 'advanced syntax layer' (Celano 2019: 288) which encodes information that can be defined as lying between syntax and semantics. This is because semantic annotation is guided by morphological and syntactic information. For instance, a noun in Genitive case can be further annotated as e.g. genitive of possession. The annotation was performed manually.

Besides the well-known Latin treebanks, the WoPoss project (Dell'Oro et al. 2020) provides a diachronic corpus of Latin texts manually annotated with modality. The annotation focuses on a selection of Latin modal markers (nouns, adjectives, verbs and morphological markers). Whenever a marker is found to be modal, the entire passage, comprising the modal marker, its scope, the participant and the modal relation, is annotated according to a fine-grained annotation scheme described in Dell'Oro (2022). The annotation of the WoPoss corpus takes inspiration from the annotation process of a previous multilingual corpus of modal passages called MODAL (Ghia et al. 2016). The corpus MODAL collects conversations in English, French and Italian that have been transcribed and manually annotated with modality. Contrarily to the WoPoss corpus, MODAL focuses on epistemic and evidential passages, that is expressions of the estimation of the speaker on the likelihood of the representation described in the clause. Both the WoPoss corpus and the MODAL corpus are available in open access.

2. Lexica and databases

Lexical resources are important for lexical semantic change analysis because they provide the senses with which the words targeted in the analysis can be associated.

The best known lexical resource is WordNet, mentioned in the previous sections because it has represented the source for building the sense inventory to manually or automatically annotate corpora. Other resources are BabelNet and Wikipedia.

Among the resources available for Spanish, besides SpSemCor and SenSem, there is the ADESSE database (García Miguel et al. and Albertuz, 2005). ADESSE (*Base de datos de verbos, Alternancias de Diátesis y Esquemas Sintáctico-Semánticos del Español*) is a lexical database which contains semantic information about the verbs contained in a 1.5 million word corpus of Spanish texts. Each verb is annotated with its sense, the verb class and the semantic role of its arguments. The purpose of this project is to have a resource to study verb valency in Spanish. The verb senses were manually retrieved from lexicographic resources of reference for Spanish.

3. Digital editions linked to lexicographic resources

Digital edition of the *Chroniques* written by Froissart. Language is Medieval French. Along with information about the source text, manuscripts and witnesses, the online digital edition also provides a special view in which the text is linked to the DMF, the online Dictionary of Medieval French.

Based on the model of the digital edition of the *Chroniques*, Chiarcos et al. (2018) published the digital edition of the *Grande chirurgie* by Gui de Chauliac. The annotation of the meanings is done by linking the digital edition to the DEAF-*Dictionnaire etymologique de l'ancien français*. The links between the lemmata of the text and the entries in the DEAF were established automatically based on the exact match of the string of characters. This has the drawback of excluding graphic variants from the linking e.g. *humeur* in the text and *umor* in the DEAF. Another issue is that the annotation is performed at the word level, and not at the sense level. This means that polysemy is not addressed. For instance, the word *humeur* in the treatise designates both « any fluid in the human or animal body », and « one of the four humors of the classical humoralism that govern the equilibria of a healthy body », i.e., blood, phlegm, yellow bile and black bile. The opposite case is also problematic: some words are attested in the text with only one sense but the dictionary registers more than one sense for the same word. The authors address the problem of polysemous words in section 9.2, saying that the sense tagging should be improved by raising it from the word level to the sense level. The original LaTeX text already provides semantic disambiguation at the lexeme level: each word is followed by its exact sense + information about technical meanings. The dictionary is also structured as a tree, with main and sub-senses. The issue is to establish the link between the lexemes in the text and the entries in the dictionary: in order to perform the linking automatically the character string of the meaning given in the mark-up must be the same as the one given in the dictionary entry, which often is not the case.

4. Tools for automatic semantic annotation

The UCREL Semantic Analysis System (USAS) is a software tool to perform automatic semantic analysis at the lexical level. The semantic tagger was originally created for English and then subsequent versions have been created to perform semantic tagging on other languages. Starting with Finnish (Löfberg et al., 2003), a multilingual version of the UCREL tool was created for 15 additional languages (Piao et al., 2015). An open source version of the tool is also available as PyMUSAS (<https://pypi.org/project/pymusas/>), a project started in 2021 and which currently covers 8 languages. The automatic semantic annotation performed by the UCREL tool is based on a tagset

of semantic macro-categories (e.g. ‘The Body and the Individual’, ‘Science and Technology’) which builds on the Longman Lexicon of Contemporary English (McArthur, 1981). The macro-categories can be further specified in different subfields (e.g. ‘Anatomy and Physiology’, ‘Information technology and computing’). The Spoken BNC2014 (Love et al. 2014), which contains transcripts of oral conversations in British English for a total of 10 million words, has been semantically tagged at the word sense level with the UCREL tagger. The annotation was not manually checked. The user can select the first option given by the tagger, but they can also access the full annotation, which comprises all possible annotations offered by the tool for the target word in context. The tagger has also been tested on a selection of different corpora, and both synchronic and diachronic data (see section 6).

Other tools for automatic semantic annotation are:

1. Idiom Tagger: Tool developed within the DutchSemCor project to automatically detect idiomatic uses of words.
<http://wordpress.let.vupr.nl/dutchsemcor/results/software-and-tools/idiom-tagger/>
2. Domain classifier: Developed within the DutchSemCor project
<http://wordpress.let.vupr.nl/dutchsemcor/results/software-and-tools/domain-classifier/>. It is trained on Cornetto database data (see above). Domain labels are associated with WordNet synsets.
3. SVM WSD: Developed within the DutchSemCor project, SVM WSD is a Word Sense Disambiguation system based on Support Vector Machines. The features are represented by using a bag-of-words model.
<http://wordpress.let.vupr.nl/dutchsemcor/results/software-and-tools/svm-wsd/>
4. TIMBL WSD: Developed within the DutchSemCor project, TIMBL WSD is a Word Sense Disambiguation system based on TIMBL, which is a machine learning based engine which implements a k-nearest neighbor machine learning approach. It can be used for training a WSD model, to annotate a text with senses, or to evaluate a WSD model.
<http://wordpress.let.vupr.nl/dutchsemcor/results/software-and-tools/timbl-wsd/>
5. UKB WSD: Open-source collection of programs for graph-based Word Sense Disambiguation. It was developed by the IXA group in the University of the Basque Country <http://ixa2.si.ehu.eus/ukb/>.

5. Tools for manual semantic annotation

Manual annotation is usually performed through annotation platforms that facilitate the annotator’s work. The sense inventory or the lexical resource that is used for the annotation is usually linked or uploaded to the platform, so that the annotator can browse through the senses established for the word. In some cases, such as INCEpTION, the annotation platform provides basic statistics on the annotation such as the labels used and the inter annotator agreement. An example of such tools is LexTag, which is a platform conceived explicitly for semantic annotation. The interface allows for linking knowledge graphs, dictionaries and other lexical and encyclopedic resources to the platform, so that the annotator can use them for the annotation task. The tool is available at <https://babelscape.com/lextag>

INCEpTION (Klie et al. 2018) is an annotation platform which allows for different levels of annotation, such as lemmatisation, PoS-tagging, morphological and syntactic annotation, including semantic annotation. It is highly customisable: it comes with a default annotation setup, which can

be enriched and changed by the annotation manager. The platform is particularly suited to projects with many annotators: it allows for the distinction of different roles in the project, such as the manager, who holds rights on any operation on the project; the curator, who can manage the annotated files and change the annotation performed by the other users; the annotator, who only has rights on the files to which they were granted access. The tool was used for the annotation of the WoPoss corpus (Dell’Oro et al. 2020) and is available at <https://inception-project.github.io/>

Analec (Landragin et al. 2012), similarly to INCEpTION, allows for managing annotation projects including the implementation of a customised annotation scheme and scheme revision. It is also possible to obtain statistics on the already performed annotations, such as frequency and correlation, which can be visualised as graphs. It is available at <http://www.lattice.cnrs.fr/Analec>

GesTALt (Montemagni et al. 2000) is an annotation workbench which manages the linguistic database and hosts different applications for different levels of linguistic annotation: SinTAS for constituent annotation; FunTAS for functional annotation; SemTAS for lexico-semantic annotation; and ValTAS for evaluation and correction of inter- and intra-level annotations. This platform was used for the annotation of the ISST (Montemagni et al. 2003), described in section 1.1.1.

TreeTrans (Bird et al. 2002) is the platform used for the manual annotation of the AnCora corpus (more specifically for the annotation of named entities). The platform allows for the visualisation of the syntactic tree, and the user can make changes on the dependency relations, the functions, labels etc. The AnCora project also used it for the annotation of named entities in the corpus.

Another annotation tool used in the AnCora project is 3LB-SAT (Semantic Annotation Tool), which was specifically used for the annotation of word senses in the AnCora project. This tool allows for multilingual semantic annotation because it refers to the lexical resource EuroWordNet for the inventory of senses.

Part of the suite Syntacticus, PROIEL Annotator (Haug et al. 2009) is one of the web-based tools used for the annotation of the treebanks of the Old IndoEuropean languages created within the PROIEL framework. <https://github.com/mlj/proiel-webapp>

Arethusa is the annotation platform used for the Ancient Greek and Latin Dependency Treebank–AGLDT (Bamman and Crane, 2011; Celano, 2019). As mentioned in section 1.2., this treebank does not provide annotation of word senses. The semantic annotation included in AGLDT concerns features at the interface between syntax and semantics, such as genitive of possession, purpose clause etc. Therefore, this tool is not suited for the annotation of word senses. Arethusa allows for linguistic annotation and curation of the annotation. It provides a visualisation of the syntactic trees, which facilitates the annotator. It allows the user to integrate the syntactic-semantic information with the syntactic dependencies. The tool is available at <https://www.perseids.org/tools/arethusa/app/#/>

Other annotation platforms with similar functions to the ones described above are MMAX2 (Müller and Strube, 2006), available at <https://github.com/ottiram/MMAX2>, and ConText (Leacock 1993), used for the annotation of the English SemCor.

6. Approaches to semantic change analysis

The resources and tools outlined in the previous section of this paper have a range of possible applications to semantic change analysis.

Semantically annotated corpora can be used for evaluating the performance of automatic semantic change detection systems. In fact, some of the resources listed among the WordNet corpora were created with the purpose of evaluating the results of automatic taggers. This was the case for e.g. the ACL-RelAcS corpus, created with the purpose of having a gold standard and evaluating the performances of the automatic annotation of the semantic relations. The UCREL USAS semantic tagger has been tested on different corpora (see Piao et al. 2004). The BNC sampler corpus and the METER corpus (Gaizasukas et al. 2001) were selected to test the tagger on modern English: the BNC sampler contains both written and spoken language in comparable size, whereas the METER corpus was selected to represent legal discourse (the corpus collects newspaper reports in all domains, but only reports on law and court events were selected from the corpus). The UCREL tagger was also tested on diachronic data, in particular on a selection of texts from the Lancaster Newsbook Corpus, which collects newsbooks from the 17th century, and on a collection of fictional works from the 18th and 19th centuries e.g. Gulliver's travels.

Semantically annotated resources can also be used to perform semantic change analysis with both a quantitative and qualitative approach. The analysis can be performed along different axes of variation. As we have just seen above, using a corpus of specialised language e.g. legal discourse in the METER corpus and comparing it with a general corpus of the same language allows for studies on language variation governed by the genre and the intended audience of the text. Semantic change analysis however focuses specifically on diachronic changes. Diachronic corpora include texts from different historical stages of the language that they represent. This allows the researcher to exploit the corpus in order to capture semantic changes over time. However, two different synchronic corpora, if compatible, can also be used in comparison to capture differences between the two stages of the language that they represent.

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References

Agirre E., Ansa O., Arregi X., Arriola J., Díaz de Ilarraza A., Pociello E. & Uria L. (2002). Methodological issues in the building of the Basque WordNet: quantitative and qualitative analysis. *Proceedings of First International WordNet Conference*. Mysore (India).

Agirre, E., Aldezabal, I., Etxeberria, J., Izagirre, E. Mendizabal, K., Pociello, E., Quintian, M. (2006). Improving the Basque WordNet by corpus annotation. *Proceedings of the Third International WordNet Conference*, pages 287-290.

Atserias, J., Rigau G., Villarejo L. (2004). Spanish WordNet 1.6: Porting the Spanish Wordnet across Princeton versions. *LREC'04*. Lisboa.

- Bamman, D. & Crane, G. 2011. The Ancient Greek and Latin Dependency Treebank. In Sporleder, C., van Den Bosch, A. & Zervanou, K. (eds.). *Language Technology for Cultural Heritage*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer. 79–89.
- Bentivogli, L., & Pianta, E. (2005). Exploiting parallel texts in the creation of multilingual semantically annotated resources: the multiseacor corpus. *Natural Language Engineering*, 11(3):247–261.
- Biagetti, E., Zanchi, C., & Short, W. M. (2021). Toward the creation of WordNets for ancient Indo-European languages. *Proceedings of the 11th Global Wordnet Conference*, 258–266. <https://aclanthology.org/2021.gwc-1.30>
- Bird, S., Maeda, K., Ma, X., Lee, H., Randall, B., Zayat, S. (2002). TableTrans, MultiTrans, InterTrans and TreeTrans: Diverse Tools Built on the Annotation Graph Toolkit. In *Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'02)*, Las Palmas, Canary Islands - Spain. European Language Resources Association (ELRA).
- BNC Consortium. 2007. British National Corpus Sampler. Oxford Text Archive. <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12024/2551>.
- Bond, F., Isahara, H., Uchimoto, K., Kuribayashi, T., Kanzaki, K. (2010). Japanese Word-Net 1.0. In *16th Annual Meeting of the Association for Natural Language Processing*, pages A5–3. Tokyo.
- Bond, F., Baldwin, T., Fothergill, R. Uchimoto, K. (2012) Japanese SemCor: A Sense-tagged Corpus of Japanese. *The 6th International Conference of the Global WordNet Association (GWC-2012)*, Matsue.
- Broda, B., Marcińczuk, M., Maziarz, M., Radziszewski, A., Wardyński, A. (2012) KPWr: Towards a Free Corpus of Polish. *Proceedings of LREC'12*, 2012.
- Camacho-Collados, J., Bovi, C. D., Raganato, A., and Navigli, R. (2019). Sensedefs: a multilingual corpus of semantically annotated textual definitions. *Language Resources and Evaluation*, 53(2):251–278
- Castellón, I., Climent, S., Coll-Florit, M., Lloberes, M., Rigau, G. (2012). Semantic hand tagging of theSenSem corpus using Spanish wordnet senses. *6th International Global Wordnet Conference*, page 72.
- Cecchini, F. M., Passarotti, M., Marongiu, P., Zeman, D. (2018). Challenges in Converting the Index Thomisticus treebank into Universal Dependencies. *Proceedings of the Universal Dependencies Workshop 2018 (UDW 2018)*, ed. by Marie-Catherine de Marneffe, Teresa Lynn, and Sebastian Schuster, 27–36. Brussels, Belgium: Association for Computational Linguistics. doi:10.18653/v1/W18-6004
- Celano, G. (2019). The Dependency Treebanks for Ancient Greek and Latin. *Digital Classical Philology*, 279–98. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110599572-016>.
- Chiarcos, C., Tittel, S. and Bermúdez-Sabel, H. (2018). Using RDFa to Link Text and Dictionary Data for Medieval French. *Proceedings of the 6th Workshop on Linked Data in Linguistics (LDL-2018)*, Miyazaki, Japan, May.
- Christiane Fellbaum (ed.). (1998) .WordNet: An Electronic Lexical Database. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

- Clackson, J. (ed.). 2011a. *A companion to the Latin language*. Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Clackson, J.. 2011b. Introduction. In James Clackson (ed.), *A companion to the Latin language*, 1–6. Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Dell’Oro, F., Bermúdez Sabel, H., Marongiu, P. (2020). “Implemented to be shared: the WoPoss annotation of semantic modality in a Latin diachronic corpus”. *Sharing the Experience: Workflows for the Digital Humanities. Proceedings of the DARIAH-CH*. <https://campus.dariah.eu/resource/events/sharing-the-experience-workflows-for-the-digital-humanities#session-8>
- Dell’Oro, Francesca (2022). *WoPoss guidelines for the annotation of modality*. Revised version. Swiss National Science Foundation. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3560950>
- Delli Bovi, C., Camacho-Collados, J., Raganato, A., and Navigli, R. (2017). EuroSense: Automatic harvesting of multilingual sense annotations from parallel text. In *Proceedings of the Association of Computational Linguistics*, volume 2, pages 594–600.
- Du Cange, C. du F., Carpenter, P., Henschel, L. G. A. & Favre, L. (1883–1887 [1678]). *Glossarium mediæ et infimæ latinitatis* [Glossary of Middle and Low Latin]. Niort: Favre.
- Francis, N. W. and Kucera, H. (1979). BROWN CORPUS MANUAL. Brown University, Rhode Island, 3 edition. (<http://khnt.aksis.uib.no/icame/manuals/brown/>)
- Gábor, K., Zargayouna, H., Buscaldi, D., Tellier, I., Charnois, T. (2016). Semantic Annotation of the ACL Anthology Corpus for the Automatic Analysis of Scientific Literature. *Proceedings of the LREC 2016 Conference*, Portoroz, Slovenia, May 2016.
- García-Miguel, J. M., Vaamonde, G., & González Domínguez, F. (2010). ADESSE, a Database with Syntactic and Semantic Annotation of a Corpus of Spanish. In Proceedings of the Seventh International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC’10). Valletta, Malta: European Language Resources Association (ELRA). http://www.lrec-conf.org/proceedings/lrec2010/pdf/859_Paper.pdf.
- Gaizauskas, R., Foster, J., Wilks, Y., Arundel, J., Clough, P., & Piao, S. (2001). The METER corpus: a corpus for analysing journalistic text reuse. In Proceedings of Corpus Linguistics 2001 (pp: 214-223). Lancaster, UK.
- Ghia, E., Kloppenburg, L., Nissim, M., Pietrandrea, P., & Cervoni, V. (2016). A Construction-centered Approach to the Annotation of Modality. In H. Bunt (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 12th Joint ACL-ISO Workshop on Interoperable Semantic Annotation* (pp. 67–74). Portoroz: ACL, ISO. Accessed 4 July 2019
- Haug, D. T. T. & Jøhndal, M. L. (2008). Creating a Parallel Treebank of the Old Indo-European Bible Translations. In C. Sporleder & Kiril Ribarov (Eds.), Proceedings of the Second Workshop on Language Technology for Cultural Heritage Data (LaTeCH 2008) (pp. 27–34).
- Haug, D. T. T., Jøhndal, M. L., Eckhoff, H., M., Welo, E., Hertenzenberg, M. J., Muth, A. (2009). 'Computational and Linguistic Issues in Designing a Syntactically Annotated Parallel Corpus of Indo-European Languages'. *Traitement automatique des langues* 50 (2): 17-45.

- Hamp, B. & H. Feldweg (1997). GermaNet - a Lexical-Semantic Net for German. *Proceedings of ACL workshop Automatic Information Extraction and Building of Lexical Semantic Resources for NLP Applications*. Madrid, 1997.
- Hatvani, C., Kuti, J., Miháltz, M., Szarvas, G. (2007). GVOP 3.1.1-2004-05-0191/3.0 – *Magyar ontológia építése és alkalmazása információkinyerő rendszerekben, projektzáró összefoglaló jelentés*. Technical Report. Szeged.
- Henrich, V. & Hinrichs, E. (2014). Consistency of Manual Sense Annotation and Integration into the TüBa-D/Z Treebank. *Proceedings of the 13th International Workshop on Treebanks and Linguistic Theories (TLT13)*, Tübingen, Germany, December 2014, pp. 62-74.
- Henrich, V., Hinrichs, E., Vodolazova, T. (2012). Webcage: a web-harvested corpus annotated withgermanet senses. *Proceedings of the 13th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, pages 387–396. Association for Computational Linguistics, EACL, Avignon, France.
- Ion, R. (2007). *Metode de dezambiguizare semantica automata. Aplicații pentru limbile engleză în română*. Ph.D. thesis, ACADEMIA ROMÂNĂ, Institutul de Cercetări pentru Inteligența Artificială, Bucurest.
- Juvonen, P. & Koptjevskaja-Tamm, M. (2016). *The Lexical Typology of Semantic Shifts*. Berlin, Boston: Mouton De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110377675>
- Klie, J.-C., Bugert, M., Boullosa, B., Eckart de Castilho, R. and Gurevych, I. (2018). The INCEpTION Platform: Machine-Assisted and Knowledge-Oriented Interactive Annotation. In *Proceedings of System Demonstrations of the 27th International Conference on Computational Linguistics (COLING 2018)*, Santa Fe, New Mexico, USA
- Koeva, S., Mihov, S., & Tinchev, T. (2004). Bulgarian Wordnet—structure and validation. *Romanian Journal of Information Science and Technology*, 7(1-2), 61-78.
- Koeva, S., Leseva, S., Tarpomanova, E., Rizov, B., Dimitrova, T., Kukova, H. (2010). Bulgarian sense annotated corpus - results and achievements. In M. Tadić, M. Dimitrova-Vulchanova, and S. Koeva, editors, *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference of Formal Approaches to South Slavic and Balkan Languages*, pages 41–48. FASSBL-7, Dubrovnik, Croatia.
- Landes, S., Leacock, C., & Fellbaum, C. 1998. Building semantic concordances. In Fellbaum, C. (ed.) *WordNet: an electronic lexical database*. Boston: Association for Computational Linguistics. 63–69.
- Landragin, F., Poibeau, T., Victorri, B. (2012). ANALEC: a New Tool for the Dynamic Annotation of Textual Data. In *Proceedings of the Eighth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'12)*, pages 357–362, Istanbul, Turkey. European Language Resources Association (ELRA).
- Leacock, C. (1993). *ConText: A tool for semantic tagging of text: User's guide*. Cognitive Science Laboratory, Princeton University: CSL Report No. 54, February 1993.
- Lewis, C. T. (1890). *An elementary Latin dictionary*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- Lewis, C. T. & Short, C. (1879). *A Latin dictionary, founded on Andrews' edition of Freund's Latin Dictionary. Revised, enlarged and in great part rewritten by Charlton T. Lewis, PhD. and Charles Short*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Löfberg, L., Archer, D., Piao, S., Rayson, P., McEnery, T., Varantola, K., Juntunen, J.-P. (2003). Porting an English semantic tagger to the Finnish language. In Dawn Archer, Paul Rayson, Andrew Wilson and Tony McEnery (eds.) *Proceedings of the Corpus Linguistics 2003 conference*. UCREL technical paper number 16. UCREL, Lancaster University. 457–464.
- Love, R., Dembry, C., Hardie, A., Brezina, V., & McEnery, T. (2017). The spoken BNC2014. *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics*, 22(3), 319-344.
- Lupu, M., Trandabat, D., Husarciuc, M. (2005). A Romanian semcor aligned to the English and Italian multiseacor. In *Proceedings 1st ROMANCE FrameNet Workshop at EUROLAN 2005 Summer School*, pages 20–27. EUROLAN, Cluj-Napoca, Romania.
- Marcinićzuk, M., Oleksy, M., Kocoń, J., Bernaś, T., Wolski, M. (2015). Towards an event annotated corpus of Polish. *Cognitive Studies | Études cognitives*.
- Maziarz, M., Piasecki, M., Rudnicka, E., Szpakowicz, S., Kędzia, P. (2016). plWordNet 3.0 – a Comprehensive Lexical-Semantic Resource. In *Proceedings of COLING 2016, the 26th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: Technical Papers*, pages 2259–2268, Osaka, Japan. The COLING 2016 Organizing Committee.
- McArthur, Tom. 1981. Longman lexicon of Contemporary English.
- Miller, G. A., Leacock, C., Teng, R., & Bunker, R. T. (1993). A semantic concordance. *Proceedings of the Workshop on Human Language Technology*, 303–308. <https://aclanthology.org/H93-1061>
- Minozzi, S. (2017). Latin WordNet, una rete di conoscenza semantica per il latino e alcune ipotesi di utilizzo nel campo dell'information retrieval. In P. Mastandrea (Ed.), *Strumenti digitali e collaborativi per le scienze dell'antichità* (pp. 123–134). Venezia: Università Ca' Foscari.
- Montemagni, S., Barsotti, F., Battista, M., Calzolari, N., Crazzari, O., Zampolli, A., Fanciulli, F., Massetani, M., Raffaelli, R., Basili, R., Pazienza, M.T., Saracino, D., Zanzotto, F., Mana, N., Pianesi, F., Delmonte, R., (2000). The Italian Syntactic-Semantic Treebank: Architecture, Annotation, Tools and Evaluation. *Proceedings of the COLING Workshop on "Linguistically Interpreted Corpora (LINC-2000)"*, Luxembourg, 6 August 2000. 18–27.
- Müller, C., Strube, M. (2006). Multi-Level Annotation of Linguistic Data with MMAX2. In: Sabine Braun, Kurt Kohn, Joybrato Mukherjee (Eds.): *Corpus Technology and Language Pedagogy. New Resources, New Tools, New Methods*. Frankfurt: Peter Lang, pp. 197-214.
- Navigli, R. and Ponzetto, S. P. (2012). BabelNet: The automatic construction, evaluation and application of a wide-coverage multilingual semantic network. *Artificial Intelligence*, 193:217–250.
- Oravecz, C., Váradi, T., Sass, B. (2014). The Hungarian Gigaword Corpus. *Proceedings of LREC 2014*, 2014.
- Pasini, T. and Navigli, R. (2017). Train-o-matic: Large-scale supervised word sense disambiguation in multiple languages without manual training data. In *Proceedings of Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, Copenhagen, Denmark.

- Pasini, T. and Camacho-Collados, J. (2020). A Short Survey on Sense-Annotated Corpora. In *Proceedings of the Twelfth Language Resources and Evaluation Conference*, pages 5759–5765, Marseille, France. European Language Resources Association.
- Passarotti M. (2019). The Project of the Index Thomisticus Treebank. In M. Berti (Ed.), *Digital Classical Philology. Ancient Greek and Latin in the Digital Revolution* (pp. 299–319). Berlin-Boston: Walter De Gruyter GmbH.
- Petrolito, T. and Bond, F. (2014). A survey of wordnet annotated corpora. In *Proceedings of the Seventh Global WordNet Conference* (pp. 236-245).
- Piao, S. S., Bianchi, F., Dayrell, C., D’egidio, A., & Rayson, P. 2015. Development of the multilingual semantic annotation system. In (Proceedings of the 2015 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies. 1268–1274.
- Piao, S. S. L., Rayson, P., Archer, D., & McEnery, T. 2004. Evaluating Lexical Resources for A Semantic Tagger. In *Proceedings of the Fourth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC’04)*. Lisbon, Portugal: European Language Resources Association (ELRA), 2004.
- Raganato, A., Delli Bovi, C., and Navigli, R. (2016). Automatic Construction and Evaluation of a Large Semantically Enriched Wikipedia. In *Proceedings of IJCAI*, pages 2894–2900, New York City, NY, USA, July.
- Roventini, A., Alonge, A., Calzolari, N., Magnini, B., Bertagna, F. (2000). ItalWordNet: a Large Semantic Database for Italian. *Proceedings of the Second International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC’00)*, Athens, Greece. European Language Resources Association (ELRA).
- Scarlini, B., Pasini, T., and Navigli, R. (2019). Just "OneSeC" for Producing Multilingual Sense-Annotated Data. In *Proceedings of the 57th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, pages 699–709.
- Schlechtweg, D., McGillivray, B., Hengchen, S., Dubossarsky, H., & Tahmasebi, N. (2020). SemEval-2020 task 1: Unsupervised lexical semantic change detection. *Proceedings of the Fourteenth Workshop on Semantic Evaluation*, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.semeval-1.1>
- Schneider, N., Mohit, B., Oflazer, K., & Smith, N. A. (2012). Coarse lexical semantic annotation with supersenses: an Arabic case study. In *Proceedings of the 50th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 2: Short Papers)* (pp. 253-258).
- Stoyanova, I., Koeva, S., & Lesseva, S. (2006). Applying and analysing Brown corpus model for Bulgarian. *The Third Inter-Varietal Applied Corpus Studies (IVACS) group International Conference on "LANGUAGE AT THE INTERFACE" 23rd - 24th June 2006, Nottingham, UK*
- Tahmasebi, N., Borin, L., Jatowt, A., Xu, Y. & Hengchen, S. (eds.). 2021. *Computational approaches to semantic change*. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Taulé, M., Martí, M. A. & Recasens, M. 2008. AnCora: Multilevel Annotated Corpora for Catalan and Spanish. In *Proceedings of the Sixth International Conference on Language Resources and*

Evaluation (LREC'08). Marrakech, Morocco: European Language Resources Association (ELRA). http://www.lrec-conf.org/proceedings/lrec2008/pdf/35_paper.pdf.

Teodorescu, D. von der Ohe, S., Kondrak, G. 2022. UAlberta at LSCDiscovery: Lexical Semantic Change Detection via Word Sense Disambiguation. In Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Computational Approaches to Historical Language Change, Dublin, Ireland. Association for Computational Linguistics. 180–186

Veronika Vincze, György Szarvas, Attila Almási, Dóra Szauter, Róbert Ormándi, Richárd Farkas, Csaba Hatvani, and János Csirik. 2008. Hungarian Word-Sense Disambiguated Corpus. In Proceedings of the Sixth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'08), Marrakech, Morocco. European Language Resources Association (ELRA).

Vossen, P. (2006). Cornetto: Een lexicaal-semantische database voor taaltechnologie. *Dixit Special Issue*, Stevin.

Vossen P., Görög, A., Laan, F., Van Gompel, M., Izquierdo, R. , Van den Bosch, A. (2011). DutchSemCor: building a semantically annotated corpus for Dutch. In *Proceedings of Electronic Lexicography in the 21st century: New Applications for new users (eLEX2011)*, Bled, Slovenia, November 10-12, 2011

Vossen P., Görög, A., Izquierdo, R. (2012). DutchSemCor: targeting the ideal sense-tagged corpus. In *Proceedings of the Eighth conference on International Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'12)*, Istanbul, Turkey.